
Series: **PHYSICS**

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Fourth Electromagnetic Induction

Annotation

Variants of electromagnetic induction are considered. It is shown that there is also an induction caused by the existence of a flow of electromagnetic energy. The dependence of emf is found. this induction on the electromagnetic energy flux density.

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1. Introduction

Below there are different options for electromagnetic induction. An induction caused by some change of the electromagnetic energy flow can be stood out. This induction is called the fourth electromagnetic induction. The dependence of the emf of this induction on the density of electromagnetic energy flux and wire parameters is determined. The mechanism of the flow of energy entering the wire and compensating for heat loss is considered.

2. Forces and fluxes of electromagnetic energy in a conductive body

The law of conservation of momentum for a body interacting with an electromagnetic field can be written in the following form [1]:

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(J) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(pV) + gV, \quad (1)$$

where

J is the mechanical momentum of the device,

p is the density of the electromagnetic momentum,

g is the flux density of the electromagnetic momentum,

V is the volume of the body, in which the electromagnetic field momentum interacts with the body, i.e. with charges in this volume.

It is important that this formula be applicable only to a body in which there are free electrical charges. Such a body is electrically conductive.

Equation (1) means that the total momentum flux in the entire volume of the field is equal to zero.

It is known that the force acting on the body is

$$F = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(J). \quad (2)$$

Consequently,

$$\frac{F}{V} = \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + g. \quad (3)$$

It is known [1] that

$$p = \frac{S}{c^2}, \quad (4)$$

$$g = \frac{S}{c}, \quad (5)$$

where S is the density of the electromagnetic energy flux. Combining (3)-(5), we find:

$$\frac{F}{V} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t}\left(\frac{S}{c^2}\right) + \frac{S}{c}. \quad (6)$$

Thus, if the electrically conductive body is in the flow of electromagnetic energy S , then force (6) acts on it, depending only on the flow of electromagnetic energy S . This force also exists at a constant flow S , and then

$$\frac{F}{V} = \frac{S}{c}. \quad (7)$$

In is possible that the flow of electromagnetic energy propagates in the body with the relative dielectric constant ε and magnetic permeability μ . In this case, the previous formulas must operate with the speed c_s of electromagnetic wave in the substance instead of the speed of light in a vacuum. So, this speed c_s is defined by

$$c_s = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu}}. \quad (8)$$

Consider the case when the vectors of electric and magnetic fields' strengths are perpendicular. Then instead of formula (6) we get:

$$\frac{F}{V} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{S\varepsilon\mu}{c^2} \right) + \frac{S\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu}}{c}. \quad (9)$$

If, moreover, the field is constant, then

$$\frac{F}{V} = \frac{S\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu}}{c}. \quad (10)$$

3. Types of electromagnetic induction

The law of electromagnetic induction is known.

$$e = \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial t}, \quad (1)$$

where Φ is the magnetic flux, e is the emf. It is also known [1] that this electromagnetic induction, namely the appearance of emf in the conductor may occur as a consequence of the fulfillment of the following two laws:

$$F = q(v \times B), \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \times E = -\frac{\partial B}{\partial t}. \quad (3)$$

In accordance with this there are the following two types of electromagnetic induction:

The first type is case (3) when in the conductor emf appears due to a change in the magnetic flux. This is the *electromagnetic induction caused by a change in the magnetic flux*.

The second type is case (2) when the emf in the conductor appears under the action of the Lorentz magnetic force due to the mutual displacement of the wire and the magnetic field without changing the magnetic flux. This is the *electromagnetic induction caused by the Lorentz force*.

The third type of electromagnetic induction arising in the unipolar Faraday generator is also known: *unipolar electromagnetic induction*. In this generator, the motor rotates a permanent magnet, and an emf is generated at the radius of the magnet. This emf is determined by the following formula:

$$e = \omega BL^2/2, \quad (4)$$

where

B is the induction of a permanent magnet,

L is the length of the radius of the magnet,

ω is the angular velocity of rotation.

This formula was obtained by different methods: in [2] using the theory of relativity and in [3] on the basis of the law of conservation of momentum.

Next, we will show that the current is induced in a conductor located in the flow of energy of an electromagnetic wave. We call *electromagnetic induction caused by the flow of electromagnetic energy* the fourth type of electromagnetic induction. The Emf of this induction is equal to the density of the forces acting on the electrical charges and arising with the advent of an electromagnetic energy flux. These forces are defined above by equations (2.9) and (2.10). Therefore, the fourth emf induction is equal to

$$\mathcal{E}_4 = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{S\varepsilon\mu}{c^2} \right) + \frac{S\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu}}{c} \quad (5)$$

or with a constant flow

$$\mathcal{E}_4 = \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{S\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu}}{c} \quad (6)$$

where γ is some coefficient. Analyzing the dimensions of the quantities included here, we find that γ has the dimension of the electric charge density. Thus, the flow of electromagnetic energy acts on an electric charge with force (6). This force is the fourth emf.

Consequently, the electromagnetic flux allows the charges (charge current) to overcome the resistance to movement and does work (which is partially converted into heat). This force acts on all charges (electrons) in the wire, directed in the direction of the current (i.e. it does not act on the wire as a whole). Thus, the flow creates an emf that “drives the current”.

On the other hand, Chapter 5 shows that the electromagnetic energy density is a function of the current density J and the magnetic field strength H , which is expressed by the following formula, see in (5.3.3):

$$S = \rho JH, \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the electrical resistance. Thus, each element of the wire with a current radiates a flux of electromagnetic energy. This energy flow penetrates the next element of the wire and creates in this element a force acting on the charges, i.e. the determined above emf fourth electromagnetic induction. This force creates current. In this way,

the current in the next element arises as a result of the flow of electromagnetic energy created by the current of the previous element.
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Note that the energy flow created by some current element can NOT affect this current element, just like the charge field cannot affect this charge.

4. Experiments

Such a view agrees well with the well-known fact that the lightning has a leader moving at a speed of several hundred kilometers per second. Here is how this process is described in [4]:

Another strong bolt of lightning, simultaneous with a bang, illuminated the entire space. I can see how a long and dazzling beam in the color of sun beam approaches to me right in the solar plexus. The end of it is sharp as a razor but further it becomes thicker and thicker, and reaches something like 0,5 meter. Further I can't see, as I am staring at a downward angle.

Instant thought that it is the end. I see how the tip of the beam approaches. Suddenly it stopped and between the tip and the body began to swell a ball the size of a large grapefruit. There was a thump as if a cork popped from a bottle of champagne. The beam flew into a ball. I see the blindingly bright ball, color of the sun, which rotates at a breakneck pace, grinding the beam inside. But I do not feel any touch, any heat.

The ball grinds the ray and increases in size. ... The ball does not issue any sounds. At first it was bright and opaque but then begins to fade, and I see that it is empty. Its shell has changed and it became like a soap bubble. The shell rotates, its diameter remained stable but the surface was with metallic sheen.

An experiment is known that can serve as an experimental proof of the existence of this induction [5]. This experiment is proposed and considered in [6, 7, 8] - see fig. 1 from [6], where

- 1 - copper conductor with a diameter of 5 mm and a length of 200 mm,
 - 2 - spiral copper wire with a diameter of 1 mm, the diameter of the spiral is 30 mm,
 - 3 - "excitation winding" around wire 2, the number of turns is 1700,
- G - galvanometer.

The main experiment consisted of the following. A direct current I_b flowed through the excitation winding. In this case, a direct current I_{np} also flowed through conductor 1, measured by a galvanometer G. Current I_b changed from 0.05 to 0.2A. In this case, a linear relationship $I_{np} = f(I_b)$ was obtained. In particular, if $I_{np} = 13\text{mkA}$, then $I_b = 0.18\text{A}$.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Another experiment was as follows. Two conductors with their helical excitation windings were connected in parallel - see fig. 2, where 1 is the first conductor, 2 is the second conductor, 3 and 4 are the excitation windings of the first and second conductor, respectively. When the excitation windings are turned on in the opposite direction, the current is

$I_{np} \approx 0$. However, with the coordinated switching on of the excitation windings, "the current values turned out to be so high that the galvanometer needle instantly went off scale", which corresponded to the current $I_{np} = 13\text{mA}$.

In [5] it is shown that these experiments are experimental proof of the existence of the fourth electromagnetic induction.

Fig. 3.

Another experiment proving the existence of the fourth electromagnetic induction is the Pozynich transformer [9]. In this transformer, the sheath and center wire are connected as transformer windings - see fig. 3. Two connection schemes are possible, when the central wire and the cable sheath are included either in the primary circuit or in the secondary circuit of the transformer. The experiments showed that in both modes the transformation ratio was equal to 1.

In both cases, the current in the primary circuit creates a magnetic strength in the secondary circuit. This strength creates a longitudinal flow of electromagnetic energy in the secondary circuit. This flow creates a fourth electromagnetic induction, which manifests itself as a force acting on the wire's electrons. This force creates a current in the secondary circuit. Finally, this current creates strength, the consequence of which is again the appearance of a flow of electromagnetic energy, and so on. This is how an electromagnetic wave propagates along an electrically conductive wire.

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